

Conversation with Professor Ken Cruickshank

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ABSTRACT

Conversation with Professor Ken Cruickshank is a key component of the multimodal approach adopted by *The University of Sydney Journal of TESOL*. In this engaging dialogue, we delve into Professor Cruickshank's passions for TESOL and TESOL research, his ongoing research endeavours, his impactful Sydney Institute for Community Language Education, and his valuable advice for PhD students on sustaining motivation throughout their academic journeys. Moreover, Professor Cruickshank shares his insights and guidance for TESOL coursework students and teachers. We trust that you will find this conversation enlightening and enriching.

Keywords: Ken Cruickshank, TESOL research, community language education, advice for PhD students, advice for TESOL postgraduate students and teachers

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THE CONVERSATION

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